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The Contribution of Technology Intelligence to Sustainable Competitiveness

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ABSTRACT

The pressure of increasing competition driven by globalization and digitalization forces The growing competition fueled by globalization and digitalization compels businesses to gain and sustain a sustainable competitive advantage (SCA) by developing strategic capabilities. In this context, Technology Intelligence (TI) emerges as an effective management tool, enabling firms to act proactively and with agility. This study examines the contribution of TI to SCA from multiple dimensions, focusing on its theoretical and practical connections with knowledge, innovation, and technology management. The article first discusses the theoretical basis of SCA and its link to firm resources. It then explores how knowledge-based competition aligns with innovation and technology management. Finally, it evaluates TI's impact on SCA through seven core functions: identifying opportunities and threats, supporting innovation, developing core competencies, strengthening strategic decision-making, fostering environmental adaptation, guiding technology transfer, and counterintelligence. TI is a holistic process that, especially when supported by AI and open source analysis, enhances firms' ability to sustain competitive advantage across all business scales.

Keywords: *Technology, Intelligence,, Sustainable, Competitive Advantage, Innovation, Entrepreneurship, Strategic Decision-Making*

1. INTRODUCTION

The transition of competition from the national to the international level has made it critical for enterprises to survive and achieve sustainable financial structures. Businesses can obtain sustainable competitive advantage by owning products and technologies that differ from those of their competitors and cannot be easily copied. In today's world, where digitalization and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are rapidly advancing, the time required to develop new products or technologies has shortened, and new ways to reach different markets quickly have emerged. In this context, it is possible to define innovation and technology as the core arguments of sustainable competitive advantage.

Companies that have embraced technology development and innovation have consistently managed to stay ahead of their competitors. In this regard, according to Forbes (2025), the world's five largest companies are Apple, Nvidia, Microsoft, Amazon, and Alphabet (Google). Their activities reveal that they are technology development oriented. The technologies developed and launched by these companies are rapidly distributed across many parts of the world, contributing to their sustainable financial structures. Consequently, businesses must continuously monitor and evaluate developments in their sector. Technology Intelligence (TI) is a discipline developed to systematically manage this monitoring process. Through TI, information is collected, analyzed, and used to support strategic decision-making after relevant planning is carried out.

Enterprises compete to gain market share and revenue with products and services that meet customer needs. Global competition has triggered technological change and led consumers to demand higher-quality services at lower costs. While initiatives such as restructuring for operational efficiency, process renewal, and total quality management are necessary, they are insufficient on their own since many firms implement them (Doğan, 2017). In today's competitive environment, focusing solely on a company's core competencies and using efficiency enhancing methods is inadequate for creating sustainable competitive advantage. The valuable knowledge and skills that create such an

advantage are also related to adapting quickly to new conditions emerging under today's changing circumstances and integrating the latest technologies developed within the framework of human needs into business strategies.

In business environments dominated by uncertainty, those who generate and/or acquire new knowledge and adapt it across all areas of the enterprise achieve competitive advantage (İraz, 2005). Thus, obtaining knowledge for competitive differentiation and applying it to business strategies within an appropriate systematic framework becomes critical. Preventing the capture of a company's key capabilities and technologies by competitors must also be considered within this scope. TI guides businesses in this process and supports business strategies that define the shape and scope of competition.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Sustainable Competitive Advantage (SCA)

The concept of sustainable competitive advantage was first addressed in the strategy literature by Porter (1985) and defined as the capacity of a firm to maintain above-average profitability over a long period of time (Porter, 1985: 11). However, in Porter's definition, the duration of the "long term" is not explicitly stated, which has led to some criticism in the literature. On the other hand, Barney (1991) defined sustainable competitive advantage as the possession of resources and capabilities that cannot be easily imitated by existing or potential competitors and based this advantage on the sustainability and inimitability of differences (Barney, 1991: 100).

Competitiveness is interpreted in two different contexts: macro and micro. From a macro perspective, "sustainable competitiveness" is defined as the ability of enterprises to gain an advantage over their competitors in pricing, designing, and producing their goods and services. From a micro perspective, it is defined as the process of delivering goods and services to customers at the right place and at appropriate prices while generating profit

in the course of these operations (Çivi, 2001). In this framework, sustainable competitive advantage is considered a strategic performance indicator that encompasses both the continuity of long-term profitability and the preservation of unique capabilities.

Sustainable competition is defined as the competitive process and the efforts to prevail among enterprises seeking to achieve economic interests and objectives in the marketplace (Papatya, 2003). The concept of competitive advantage has been examined in detail in works published in the fields of management and strategy and has been explained within the framework of different theoretical approaches. In this context, various theoretical perspectives stand out in the literature. The first of these is the industry analysis approach, which emphasizes the importance of market position and industrial structure (Porter, 1980). This approach argues that the structural characteristics of the industry and the firm's position within it are decisive in achieving competitive advantage.

Conversely, knowledge-based approaches highlight the role of learning organizations, particularly in the new economy environment, where the production and utilization of knowledge have become the primary source of competitive advantage (Senge, 1990). Furthermore, in today's markets, where technology is rapidly advancing, and global competition is intensifying, the unique resources, core competencies, and adaptive capabilities of firms to environmental changes are evaluated within the framework of resource-based approaches (Barney, 1991; Teece et al., 1997). These different perspectives reveal that gaining and sustaining competitive advantage requires a structure endowed with diverse capabilities.

Sustainable competitive advantage has become the strategic focus of enterprises not only in terms of short-term performance improvements but also in maintaining and strengthening long term market positioning. In this regard, the tangible and intangible resources that enterprises possess, as well as the capabilities that enable the effective use of these resources, form the fundamental building blocks of sustainable competitive advantage. These include rare and well-integrated resources within the organization, such

as intellectual capital, corporate knowledge, and learning capacity, which are not easily imitable. These elements derive their strategic significance not only from internal capabilities but also from the dynamic analysis of the external environment and the alignment of market opportunities with these resources.

The resource-based view posits that the primary factor in achieving sustainable competitive advantage lies in the possession of unique, valuable, rare, difficult to imitate, and organizationally embedded resources. Barney (1991) laid the foundation for this approach. According to the resource based view, a firm's internal resources and capabilities are the basis of competitive differentiation, and as long as these resources cannot be easily acquired by competitors, they provide the firm with sustainable superiority. Another approach, market orientation, is based on the understanding that enterprises identify current and potential customer needs, share this information across all business units, and develop strategies that create value accordingly. The essence of this approach is the ability to manage the value creation process for the customer across all the functions of the enterprise. Developed by scholars such as Day, Narver, and Slater, this approach encompasses customer orientation, competitive responsiveness, and coordinated marketing activities. To achieve sustainable competitive advantage, enterprises must be able to consider the resource based view and the market orientation approach together.

The interaction of these two approaches enables firms to both strategically structure their internal resources and develop agile marketing strategies by continuously considering customer needs. The continuity of core competencies is directly related to the institutionalization of innovation and learning processes within the firm. Thus, sustainable competitive advantage becomes not a static superiority but a dynamic strategic capability that is constantly renewed, developed, and able to adapt rapidly to environmental changes.

One of the critical steps to achieving sustainable competition is the clear definition and implementation of a competitive strategy. Competitive strategies are defined as the set of

Figure 1. Porter's Five Forces Model

decisions and actions aimed at creating value for customers in a particular market and achieving competitive superiority through core competencies. Success in the industry depends on the competitive strategies chosen and implemented (Ülgen & Mirze, 2004). To analyze the competitive conditions faced by enterprises, it would be appropriate to base the assessment on Porter's Five Forces Model (Figure 1).

Firms operating in a sector are not only in competition with one another but must also contend with factors such as the bargaining power of suppliers and customers, the threat of substitute products, and the possibility of new entrants to the market. It is clearly evident that achieving long-term competitive advantage is directly related to technology development and innovation. However, in this context, it is necessary to exclude sectors where entry is restricted by legal regulations or where entry barriers are high due to substantial capital requirements.

The ability of companies to create added value and differentiate this value from that of their competitors, while also guiding their suppliers and customers through the technologies they develop, can provide an opportunity to control the entry of substitute products and new competitors into the market. An example of this can be seen in the renewable energy sector in Turkey, particularly in the field of solar energy. Initially, large investors and publicly supported projects were at the forefront, but over time, smaller and private firms have also entered the market. However, entry barriers in this sector are relatively high; factors such as licensing processes, infrastructure investments, and technical competence pose challenges to new ventures. Existing firms have made technological investments along the value chain from energy production to distribution for example, smart meters, remote monitoring systems, and energy storage solutions to improve their service quality and efficiency. In doing so, they have increased their preference among both government institutions and individual consumers by providing more reliable and controllable services. The technological infrastructure developed by renewable energy firms has both reduced operational costs and, although not legally required, established a quality standard that makes it more difficult for new entrants to compete. Therefore, in this sector, achieving lasting success requires not only producing energy but also generating innovation based solutions throughout the entire value chain. In this context, it is of great importance to regularly analyze each of Porter's five competitive forces and support them with appropriate strategies to attain a sustainable competitive advantage.

2.2 Knowledge, Innovation and Technology Management

Knowledge is an important asset that guides enterprises toward their objectives, contributes to innovation, and can be utilized as a source of sustainable competitiveness (Yiğit & Özyer, 2011). Today, one of the most significant factors that can distinguish enterprises from their competitors is the critical knowledge they possess. By processing this knowledge through various methods, enterprises can develop their own capabilities and differentiate themselves from others in producing competitive solutions. It is also possible to define the knowledge they generate as organizational knowledge.

Organizational knowledge is a critical resource that enables firms to differentiate themselves from competitors and gain competitive advantage.

The acquisition of such knowledge from accurate sources, its classification, and its processing through appropriate methods and techniques are ensured by a well designed knowledge management system. The ability of enterprises to transfer the knowledge they have acquired and rendered usable through proper systems into their products and services is closely related to their innovation capabilities, which are defined as one of the most important sources of competitive advantage. Innovation is defined as the implementation of a new or significantly improved product, service, or process, a marketing method, or organizational management in internal business practices, external relations, or work organization (Oslo, 2005). In this context, it can be observed that innovations derived from the knowledge possessed by enterprises pave the way for various advantages not only in their products and services but also in their internal processes. Evaluating innovation opportunities within the enterprise from a broad perspective and utilizing them wherever potential is identified can play an accelerating role in the discovery of new capabilities that will create competitive advantage such as producing a product or service for the first time, implementing a differentiated and efficient management system, or reaching a different market.

The sustainability of technologies obtained through innovation and the maintenance of the advantage gained are possible only through a well structured technology management strategy. Technology management is defined as “the linking of engineering science and management disciplines to plan, develop, and implement the technological capabilities needed to shape and achieve an organization’s strategic and tactical goals” (Judd, 1993). The degree to which enterprises can effectively design and implement technology management will directly affect their competitive advantage. Possessing technologies is not only the result of innovations made but can also be achieved through various technology transfer methods. Enterprises that have achieved success by establishing appropriate technology management systems can sustain their competitive advantage by

penetrating different markets and countries through technology transfer methods such as acquisitions, licensing, experience sharing agreements, foreign direct investments, joint ventures, and R&D collaborations, thereby gaining an additional source of strength.

2.3 Technology Intelligence (TI)

Defined as a subbranch of scientific and technical intelligence, Technology Intelligence (TI) investigates and monitors the scientific and technical activities, publications, projects, patents, and product development strategies of target countries, companies, or individuals (JP 2-0 Joint Intelligence, 2013: 37). TI is directly influential in the success of technology development efforts that can provide enterprises with significant advantages in terms of competition. TI is defined as a process that encompasses the activities of collecting and analyzing information on technological developments and delivering this information to those in need, with the aim of supporting a company's technological and strategic decisions (Lichtenthaler, 2004).

TI has been shaped within the framework of two main schools of thought: the first develops methods aimed at forecasting future technological changes, while the second emphasizes the necessity of developing systems to continuously observe and evaluate the technological environment. The second school advocates that TI is a systematic process that must remain dynamic and be updated over time, and most publications in the field support this approach.

The TI process, which corresponds to the steps of the classical intelligence cycle, consists of planning/organizing, information collection, data analysis, and dissemination of the findings. In a well planned and goal-oriented TI process, one of the critical stages is the collection of necessary information. At this stage, scientific publications and conference presentations, product catalogs, social media posts, patents, trade fairs, and similar sources can be used for information gathering. In order to assess the value of the collected information and render it meaningful for the intended purpose, analytical methods such as bibliometric analyses, patent analyses, technology assessment, benchmarking and

foresight analyses, technology and product roadmaps, multi-criteria decision-making methods, the Delphi method, scenario analyses, S-curve analysis, and portfolio analysis can be employed.

3. CONTRIBUTION OF TECHNOLOGY INTELLIGENCE TO SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE(SCA)

In order to achieve sustainable competitive advantage and maintain this strategic superiority, enterprises must establish living systems. In this context, a well-planned and effectively implemented TI system can make direct contributions to various areas of vital importance for SCA. These areas can be defined as follows.

3.1. Identification of Opportunities and Threats

TI enables enterprises to systematically monitor developments in the technological environment, thereby allowing them to detect, at an early stage, potential opportunities—such as emerging technologies and new ways of doing business as well as possible threats, such as rival technologies and the shortening of product life cycles (Lichtenthaler, 2004). Accordingly, enterprises can restructure their strategic orientations and operational activities in line with the findings obtained, making it possible to closely monitor opportunities and threats in today's rapidly changing competitive environment.

3.2. Supporting Innovation

Knowledge serves not only as a guide for enterprises in achieving their objectives but also contributes to innovation and can be used as a source of sustainable competitive advantage (Yiğit & Özyer, 2011). TI ensures the acquisition of strategic and up to date information, which constitutes the core input of innovation processes. In particular, the systematic monitoring of data related to rival technologies, market dynamics, and user needs, along with scientific and technological developments, is a critical source of information for the design and development of new product, process, or service

innovations. In this regard, TI functions as an important tool in supporting innovation management processes by identifying which types of innovation have the potential to enhance corporate competitive advantage. Thus, TI enables enterprises not only to adapt to current competitive conditions but also to develop proactive strategies and sustainably increase their innovative capacity.

3.3. Development of Core Competencies

The systematic analysis of an enterprise's existing organizational and technological capabilities and the strategic matching of these capabilities with opportunities arising in the external environment constitute an important aspect of competitiveness (Yıldız & Genç, 2020). Technology Intelligence (TI) can provide a sound and reliable infrastructure for the analysis of the organizational and technological competencies of enterprises and the identification of opportunities in the environment. At the same time, by monitoring the technological capabilities, R&D investments, and innovative activities of rival firms, TI provides critical information for enterprises to strengthen their own core competencies or develop new areas of expertise (Doğan, 2017). This process is particularly significant in terms of Sustainable Competitive Advantage (SCA). The creation and preservation of competencies that are not easily imitated by other players in the sector in which the enterprise operates, and that create value with their unique characteristics, form the basis of long-term strategic advantage. Therefore, TI practices enable not only the monitoring of environmental threats and opportunities but also the strategic guidance of internal capability management from a strategic perspective.

3.4. Strengthening Strategic Decision-Making Processes

TI directly contributes to strategic planning processes by systematically collecting and analyzing information on technology trends, market dynamics, and the strategic orientations of competitors, and presenting it to senior management (Lichtenthaler, 2004). Through this process, managers are able to make more informed, predictable, and accurate decisions in competitive environments with high levels of uncertainty. The verified, up to date, and contextual information provided by TI allows enterprises to direct

their resources effectively, identify areas that can generate competitive advantage, and develop strategic positioning in these areas. Thus, TI not only strengthens information-based decision making mechanisms but also enables enterprises to compete in the right markets, with the right technologies, and with appropriate timing. Competing in the right field and in the right way is highly profitable; however, it can only be sustained for a limited period. At this point, the assets and capabilities of the enterprise form the foundation of sustainable competitive advantage and long-term performance (Doğan, 2017).

3.5. Decision-Making on Technology Transfer and Acquisition

Technology Intelligence (TI) systematically contributes to enabling enterprises to identify the critical technologies they need or those that can provide a competitive advantage in order to achieve their current and future strategic objectives (Htun et al., 2020). In this respect, TI not only addresses the question of which technologies are necessary but also provides guidance on how these technologies should be acquired. The analyses offered by TI serve as an important input for determining whether it would be more effective for the enterprise to develop the relevant technologies inhouse from scratch or to obtain them through external sources. Particularly in technology transfer processes, TI allows for comparative evaluations among different acquisition methods such as licensing, strategic partnerships, joint ventures, mergers and acquisitions, or outsourcing (Eren & Kılıç, 2015). Thus, TI becomes a critical managerial tool that guides decisionmakers not only in the identification of technological needs but also in the development of the most appropriate acquisition strategy to meet those needs.

3.6. Protecting Technological Superiority (Counterintelligence)

One of the important dimensions of TI involves counterintelligence activities. Attempts by rival actors to obtain the technological knowledge and innovations developed by enterprises through various means constitute serious risks threatening the sustainability of technological superiority. In this context, TI not only monitors technological opportunities and threats in the external environment but also contributes to the

development of defensive strategies aimed at ensuring internal information security and protecting critical technological knowledge. Especially in a digitalizing world, increasing cyber threats and intensified competition in various sectors are prompting enterprises to adopt a more proactive and holistic approach to intelligence management. Furthermore, the proliferation of open source intelligence (OSINT) techniques makes TI applications accessible not only to large scale organizations but also to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and entrepreneurs. TI activities conducted using data obtained from open sources, with their lower cost and more flexible structures, make it possible for resource-constrained enterprises to actively participate in technology development and strategic decision making processes. This, in turn, enables even small enterprises to sustain their innovative activities and secure a position in the market, particularly in sectors where technology based competition is a determining factor.

4. CONCLUSION

This study has comprehensively addressed the critical role played by Technology Intelligence (TI) practices in the process of achieving Sustainable Competitive Advantage (SCA) in a globalizing and digitalizing competitive environment, and in transforming it into long term strategic success. Today, the speed of technological change, the diversification of customer expectations, the shortening of product life cycles, and the emergence of new market dynamics compel enterprises to move beyond traditional competitive strategies. In this context, TI is considered not merely as a process of collecting and analyzing information, but also as a holistic management support tool that directs technology based transformation within enterprises and provides strategic flexibility.

In the first part of the article, the evolution of the SCA concept and its relationship with knowledge, capability, and technology were discussed in light of the literature. The sustainability of competitive advantage depends not only on tangible assets but also on intangible and hard to imitate resources such as organizational learning, intellectual

capital, innovation capacity, and the ability to adapt to environmental changes (Barney, 1991; Teece et al., 1997). The effective management of such resources requires the continuous monitoring of both the internal dynamics of the enterprise and external environmental factors. At this point, TI practices serve as an important bridge between internal and external resources.

In the second part, the link between knowledge, innovation, and technology management was detailed, and how knowledge based competitive advantage integrates with innovation processes was explained. The organizational knowledge possessed by enterprises and their capacity to process this knowledge play a significant role not only in differentiating products and services but also in determining the innovations to be made in managerial and organizational processes. In these processes, the data driven insights provided by TI both nourish the formation of innovative ideas and facilitate the transformation of these ideas into concrete, applicable technological solutions.

In the third part, the contributions of TI to SCA were structured under seven main functional dimensions: early detection of opportunities and threats, support for innovation, development of core competencies, strengthening of strategic decision making processes, adaptation to environmental changes, optimization of technology acquisition decisions, and protection of technological superiority. These dimensions demonstrate that TI is not merely a knowledge management tool but can also be used as a strategic governance mechanism.

One of the most fundamental advantages offered by TI is enabling enterprises to become actors that not only follow technological developments but also anticipate and shape them. The holistic analysis of emerging technologies, competitors' R&D activities, evolutionary trends in the market, and scientific publication/patent activities provides enterprises with the opportunity to develop future oriented scenarios and produce strategies in line with these scenarios. In this framework, TI functions like a “strategic

radar,” allowing enterprises both to seize opportunities in a timely manner and to establish defensive mechanisms against potential threats (Lichtenthaler, 2004).

Moreover, the applicability of TI not only to large and technology intensive firms but also to SMEs and new ventures signifies the democratization of competitive advantage. TI processes conducted alongside open source intelligence (OSINT) techniques produce low cost yet high strategic value outputs, enabling even resource constrained enterprises to innovate and secure a place in the market.

In conclusion, TI serves as a fundamental lever in transforming enterprises in today’s business world into institutions capable of anticipating competition, responding agilely, and developing proactive strategies. In this respect, TI deserves further study both from a literary perspective as a distinct interdisciplinary research field, and from a practitioner’s perspective as an indispensable component of strategic decision making processes. Future research on topics such as sectoral comparisons of TI practices, their integration with digital tools, and AI supported analytical mechanisms holds the potential to make significant contributions to the literature.

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